

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

WOMENS WITH VASCULAR HEADACHES AND IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA IN PRODUCTIVE AGE AND OUTCOMES OF USING OF IRON TABLETS FOR TREATMENT

¹Dr Hamza Abdul Malik, ²Dr Syeda Fatima Tu Zahira, ³Dr Qurat Ul Ann Butt

¹Medical Officer, Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital Rahim Yar Khan

²House officer, Mayo Hospital Lahore

³House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Objective: We can classify the migraine into two groups of vascular and chronic headaches. Also the womens which are in the productive age in the world among them the most common type of anemia is iron anemia. The aim of our study is to examine the association between the vascular headache and iron anemia and also examine the results of the iron deficiency tablets which are using for these headaches by the womens who are in the productive age.

Methodology: The design of our research work was quasi control clinical trial study. Fifty womens were the part of our research work, who were in the productive age and who had the iron deficiency anemia and vascular headaches. The treatment of those patients were carried out for three months and they were treated with ferrous sulfate tablets. for the confirmation of the treatment the hemoglobin of the patients was checked after the treatment of the one month and if there was any improvement noted in any patient, then that patient was excluded from the study. During the treatment the patients who had the headache attacks and the medicines he used to relieve the pain before and three months after the start of the treatment of the ferrous sulfate were noted.

Results: The number of patients who had the headache attacks one month before the treatment was 19.6 ± 28 and the patients who had the headache attacks during the treatment was 14.2 ± 11.2 and also the patients the who the attacks after the treatment of the three months was 13.3 ± 16.1 which is ($p < 0.0001$) respectively. Moreover, the analgesics which were used before the treatment were 30.1 ± 14.1 , the analgesics which were during the treatment were 14.3 ± 11.2 , and which were used after the treatment of the three months were 13.1 ± 16.1 , which were ($p < 0.0001$) respectively.

Conclusion: It has been found out that for the treatment of the vascular headaches the iron tablets are very useful and in addition it has also very good effects on those who are suffered from iron deficiency anemia with headaches.

Key Words: Physiopathology, headaches, Disorder, Tension, Iron deficiency anemia, Anxiety.

Corresponding author:**Dr.Hamza Abdul Malik,**

Medical Officer, Sheikh Zayed Medical College and Hospital,
Rahim Yar Khan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hamza Abdul Malik et al., *Women's With Vascular Headaches And Iron Deficiency Anemia In Productive Age And Outcomes Of Using Of Iron Tablets For Treatment.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

The most common type of health complaint in the world is headache and at least more than ninety percent of people had a headache complaint once a year, and treatment of headache is one of the prime goal of health intervention. The headaches which are called the vascular and tension headaches are to be characterized the chronic headaches and also they are the main causes of headaches, and also in which the common cause for the vascular and chronic headaches is to be classified as migraine. Due to the high prevalence rate vascular and chronic headaches this disease is to be considered as the most important diseases which is mostly present in 6% in males and 15% in females, also this disease is the major cause of the economic loss, absent from the work place, from the education institute and uses a huge amount of medicine to reduce the pain. According to the World Health Organization, due to the severity the headache is to be placed on nineteenth rank among the debilitating disorder which results from migraine. Actually the headaches which are due to the tension are to be describe as chronic headache disorder and these headaches are normally connected with stress and fatigue however the occurrence of these headaches are normally slow, the severity of these headaches have variations and also these headaches are lasting for a few days.

Mostly the common form of vascular headaches is migraine which do not have specific physiopathology, but the design of multi-gene with inheritance plays a significant role. According to the reports of the recent studies the flow of blood to the brain was reduced due to the migraine attacks. There are few risk factor which are the causes of vascular and tension headaches are anxiety, irritation, consuming of medicines and dietary disorder. Similarly, in some other studies it is reported that the disorder in the blood circulation which is present in the form of iron deficiency anemia is also one of the major cause of chronic headaches. According to other research studies the headache is also a sign of iron deficiency but its relation and headache type with anemia is not mentioned. The most common type of anemia is iron deficiency anemia. Clinical symptoms of anemia are different depending on the severity of anemia from no symptoms to symptoms such as: fatigue, irritability, and headaches. According to medical text, those headaches which are due to permanent iron deficiency and they are elusive and usually they are on the frontal area. Moreover, the frequency of these headaches do not change.

The most common type of headaches which are presents in the women in the productive age are

vascular headaches. The iron deficiency anemia is most frequent in women with vascular headache. According to the findings of our study we have found out that the treatment effects of anemia in improving vascular headache in the women in the productive age and also who are the patients of iron deficiency anemia.

METHODOLOGY:

The design of this research was quasi control trial study in which we investigated the women in the reproductive age which was using the iron tablets for the vascular headache (VH). The data was calculated on 50 patients which sample size was based on $\alpha=0.05$ and $\beta=0.20$. A written consent was taken from the patients and the ethical committee approved the study. When the patients were investigated and the type of headache was determined by the neurologist and also the blood tests were carried out, the cases were selected from the patients who had the headaches and they were referred to the neurology department. The index of international headache society was used for determining the vascular headache. And if it is essential then the CT scan, MRI and EEG was used. Moreover, the neurologists used the ferritin serum, hemoglobin, hematocrit and CBC tests for determining the iron deficiency anemia. Only those patients were included in the research who in the reproductive age and they were the patients of the iron deficiency anemia and also in which the rate of hemoglobin was less than 12 mg/dl, the hematocrit was less than 34% and ferritin serum was below than 15mg/dl, clinical determination of migraine without aura which is accompanied either by five headache attacks and two headache symptom from 4 to 72 hours duration of attacks, one sided and pulsating, stopping daily activities and intensified with the activities, accompanied with nausea, vomiting, photophobia, fear of sound, recovering with sleeping; or at least two headache attacks with three features of one or more reversible aura symptoms with the minimum duration of four and maximum duration of 60 minutes, having headaches at the same time or before the aura or at least 10 headache attacks with the symptom of tension headaches. In the duration of our study the patients whose headaches were investigated and they were not having the pure migraine, and those patients which were not available in the time of examination they were excluded from the study.

The patients who were participating in our study, before the start of the treatment they were asked about their headache attacks, type and also during the last month before the treatment the painkiller they were consumed. For the treatment of the anemia the patients

were received the 60mg ferrous sulfate tablets. During the treatment (one month after beginning) and three months after the treatment, these features were examined again. Also, the patients' level of hemoglobin was examined before and after the treatment. This is a double blind study since the neuro-specialist and the interviewer were not aware of the treatment. The collected data were analyzed by a paired t- test, Wilcoxon test and repeated measurement analysis in the SPSS statistical software (version 16). P value < 0.05 was considered as significant.

RESULTS:

The patients which were the participants of this research study were the age of 29.31 ± 7.6 years old. Four patients among them were suffered from migraine with aura (8%), 30 patients were suffered from migraine without aura (60%), and also there is 16 patients with the 32% who were suffered from tension headache.

Table - 1 Causes of Attacks and the Painkiller Used in the Productive Age

Variables	One Month Before Treatment	Treatment Period	Three Months After Treatment	P Value
Mean of painkiller	19.6 \pm 12.8	14.2 \pm 11.2	13.3 \pm 11.8	<0.001
Painkiller	30.1 \pm 14.1	14.3 \pm 11.2	16.1 \pm 13.1	<0.001

The hemoglobin average level of the patients was 11 ± 9 before the treatment and after the treatment the level was increased after the treatment 12.5 ± 4 respectively ($p < 0.0001$). According to the findings of our research which had been shown in the Table-1, the frequency of attacks and use of painkiller by the patients in one month before the treatment, during the treatment and three months after the treatment were analyzed and it had been found out that the number of attacks were increased significantly and also the use of painkiller ($p = 0.01$) but after the complete treatment we compare both the time periods, one month before the treatment and one month after the treatment ($p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION:

In the results of our study we have shown that after the prescription of the iron tablets for the patients who are suffered from vascular headache and iron deficiency anemia minimize the severity the of headache attacks at the end of our study. also in the duration of the treatment period the ferrous sulfate tablets was prescribed, and before the participation in the study the patients used less painkiller. Furthermore, the painkiller which was used before the study was changed from strong ones to simple ones such as from opioids and ergotamine to acetaminophen during the study.

According to a review 40 patients which was conducted in 2001 in America showed that if the nutritional status and quality of life of the patients is improved than it will significantly reduce the intensity of the headaches in the 80% of patients. Another study which was conducted in Iran, showed that if we carried out a massage of neck and shoulder for 5 weeks continuously, which should be 4 times per day and the duration of the massage should be for 20 minutes then the 25 patients who are suffered from tension headaches, their headaches could be reduces headache up to 57% in second week, 39% in third week and 52% in fourth week after the start of the massage. In view of studies which was done on the migraine, we did not

found anything which shows the relationship between the migraine and iron deficiency anemia. A study was conducted on 56 patients in Brazil in the year of 2005 by Sylvia et al who were suffered from the anemia cell cycle and in the results of the study 50% of the patients had sever migraine without aura. another study was also conducted in Portland in 2005, the participant of that study were 50 children's which were the patients of anemia cell cycle and in the results 43.8% of children had migraine without aura and 6.2% of children had migraine with aura. Results of all these studies are similar to another study which was conducted in 2005 in America. In this study, lack of some factors such as Riboflavin, Magnesium, and iron was pointed out the as reasons for these headaches.

In the results of our study we have found that the patients who had the tension headaches had the high percentage of iron deficiency anemia (56.6%). According to the results of our study the significance of minimizing the headache attacks and he consumption of the painkiller, it seems that the findings need more attention and also this topic need to wider investigated.

However, migraine is a long lasting, progressive and debilitating disorder which affected the quality of life

of millions of peoples around the world. And also the most common type of anemia in the women is iron deficiency anemia and significantly in those women which are in the productive age therefore it is very important to accurate diagnose and quick treatment in girls and womens should carried out to avoid the lengthy sickness and to reduced quality of life which are directly the main causes of migraine. Even though one of the sign of the headache is iron deficiency, so if the treatment of the anemia is carried out properly then it will reduce the occurrence and intensity of headache attack in the patients. The results of our study shown that the headache which is due to the iron deficiency anemia will remain during the life time.

CONCLUSION:

In the results of our study we have shown a significant difference in number of attacks and the painkiller which was used by the patients being treated by ferrous sulfate. In the results of our study we have seems that the use of iron tablets has a significant effect on the treatment of vascular headaches.

REFERENCES:

1. Martin VT, Taylor F, Gebhardt B, Tomaszewski M, Ellison JS, Martin GV, et al. Allergy and Immunotherapy: Are They Related to Migraine Headache? *Headache: J Head and Face Pain* 2011;51(1):8-20.
2. Silva GS, Vicari P, Figueiredo MS, Junior HC, Idagawa MH, AR. M. Migraine mimicking headache and sickle cell disease: a transcranial Doppler study. *Cephalalgia* 2006;26(6):678-683.
3. Palermo TM, Platt-Houston C, Kiska RE, Berman B. Headache symptoms in pediatric sickle cell patients. *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol* 2005;27(8):420-424.
4. Stovner LJ, Hagen K, Jensen R, Katsarava Z, Lipton RB, Scher AI, et al. The global burden of headache: a documentation of headache prevalence and disability worldwide. *Cephalalgia*. 2007;27(3):193-210.
5. Lewis DW. Pediatric migraine. *Neurologic Clinics* 2009;27(2):481-501.
6. Winter AC, W. H, Meisinger C, Evers S, Vennemann M, Pfaffenrath V, et al. Association between lifestyle factors and headache. *J Headache Pain* 2011;12(2):147-155.
7. Greenberg DA, Aminofh MJ, Simon RP. *Clinical neurology*. New York: Mac Graw Hill; 2002.
8. Evans RW, Seifert TD. The challenge of new daily persistent headache. *Headache: J Head and Face Pain* 2011;51(1):145154.
9. Bogdanov VB, Multon S, Chauvel V, Bogdanova OV, Prodanov D, Makarchuk MY, et al. Migraine preventive drugs differentially affect cortical spreading depression in rat. *Neurobiology of Disease* 2010;41(2):430-435.
10. Kasper DL, Braunwald E, Fauci A, Hauser S, Longo D, Jamesom J. *Harrisons principle of internal medicine*. New York: Mac Graw Hill; 2005.
11. Millea PJ, Brodie JJ. Tension-type headache. *American Family Physician* 2002;66(5):797-806.
12. Kachuee H, Ameli J, Sharifi M, Tavallaei A, Keshavarzi N, Karamey GR. Evaluation of Provocating Factors of Migraine Attacks. *Kowsar Med J* 2006;11(3):279-284.
13. Wiebe ER, Trouton KJ, Eftekhari A. Anemia in early pregnancy among Canadian women presenting for abortion. *Int J Gynecology & Amp; Obstetrics* 2006;94(1):6061.
14. Hallman M, Ronald SH, Edward J, Howard L. *Cohen hematology*. New York: Mac Graw Hill; 2005.
15. Ropper AH, Samuels MA. *Adams and victor's principle of neurology*. New York: Mac Graw Hill; 2001.
16. Hilla A. Migraine headache; diagnosis and managment. *Optometry J Am Optom Assoc* 2009;80(3):138-148.
17. James Sensenig ND, Jeffrey Marrongelle DC, CCN MJ, Staverosky. T. Treatment of migraine with targeted nutrition focused on improved assimilation and elimination. *Altern Med Rev* 2001;6(5):488-494.
18. Elahie N, Jalali M, Haghighi M, Rahzani K. Effectiveness of massage on intensity and frequency of headache in women. *Scientific Med J* 2006;4(4):303-307.